

Role of NGOs of Indigenous Peoples for their Development: A Study of Nepal

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- Dil Prasad Magar¹
dilprasadmagar@gmail.com
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Abstract

This paper discusses the role of the two NGOs (INWOLAG and EMMF) of indigenous nationalities of Nepal in their development. This paper has been prepared based on both primary and secondary data, as well as theoretical review. The role of the NGOs has been discussed in relation to the empowerment theory of development (specifically its major four elements, viz., access to information, inclusion and participation, accountability, and local organizational capacity), suggested by the World Bank (2002). The role of the INWOLAG was found to be greater in its specific thematic issue (legal rights of the indigenous nationalities' women). In the same way, EMMF's role was equally important in the socioeconomic development of the marginalized communities of mid-western Nepal. Based on this discussion, we can say that NGOs of indigenous nationalities are playing a role of development actor and agent in Nepal. In the view of empowerment theory, these NGOs are contributing to empowering their own community. The role of the NGOs can be discussed in the perspective of different theories such as agency theories, Sen's capability theory, and even in another angle, e.g., NGOs' role as intermediary, planner, implementer, participant, etc.

Key words: NGOs, indigenous nationalities, INWOLAG, EMMF, role, development.

¹ Dil Prasad Magar is a researcher and independent consultant of the development field in Nepal. Mr Magar is associated with HDRC Nepal and Sansthaagat Bikas Sanjal.

Introduction

Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) sector is one of the key actors of the development. In Nepal, the political transition after the 1990 led many NGOs to emerge to contribute in nation's development. More than 60,000 NGOs so far have been working in Nepal with plethora of programs and activities (ADB, n.d. as cited in IPE, FBC and CPRA, 2010, p. 5). The figure though varies as per the sources; for instance Nepal's three year interim plan (2007-2009) document mentioned 22, 685 registered NGOs in Nepal (NPC, 2007) and the current three year plan (2010 -2012) document mentions that around 27,000 Nepali NGOs and more than 220 INGOs are actively working in various sectors of development of Nepal (NPC, 2010, p. 174). The increasing number of NGOs is often attributed to focus in addressing the various types of issues of the different communities.

After April of 1990 or re-establishment of the democracy by the people's movement in Nepal, various deprived groups, marginalized communities like ethnic communities expected to get mainstreamed in various sectors of the state which unfortunately did not take place in practice. Due to raising awareness and freedom, selected educated individuals of these communities/groups created a concept to establish NGOs for the development of primarily their own community/groups. Then, this trend is still continued. Indigenous nationalities/ethnic communities also established many NGOs and many of them are actively working as per their vision. Major focus sectors of these NGOs are related to their own issues like social empowerment, education, advocacy for their rights, income and employment etc.

This paper discusses the role of the two NGOs of indigenous nationalities of Nepal in their development. This paper highlights the social dimension of the development of the indigenous nationalities/ethnic communities rather than economic, political and other.

Theoretical Framework

When the actor oriented approach to development was emerged then the notion of local/insider/people-centred, third-world focused, right-based approach, indigenous development etc. also came with its complementary. Sardan (1995) mentions the advantage of an actor oriented approach that it grasps issues of the ‘social life’ of development (from conception to realization) as well as the responses and lived experiences of the social actors (as cited in Long & Long, 1992, p. 14). A research done in Nepal and Bangladesh shows that use of actor-oriented tools can change perceptions of development actors, encouraging them to engage with the social and political context of their activities in a productive way (Biggs & Motsaert, 2004, p. i). This approach gives importance to the most disadvantaged people, who are often by-passed by the state or donors; local resource mobilization and more cost-effectiveness; participatory approach to development is fostered. In our context, NGOs of the indigenous nationalities are somehow similar to the actor-oriented approach to development for themselves.

The NGOs should have those roles due to which the community peoples may feel being an able to fulfill the needs and feel freedom, like Sen’s ‘development as freedom’. Specific community based NGOs can be effective for their own development. This development practice depends on five principles viz. (1.) the need to feel good about oneself, (2.) the need to belong and feel secure, (3.) the need to feel in control of one’s life, (4.) the need to be free, active and independent, and (5.) the need to support one’s family (Maiava, 2001, p. 219 -220). Accepting these principles, to some extent, NGOs of the indigenous nationalities in our context are considered as initiator for their own development.

Intentional development always focus on ‘what should be there’ leaving ‘what is actually happening and what people are doing anyway’ and cultures are assumed to be passive, static and

restrictive (Maiava & King, 2007, p. 95). Furthermore, external agents are not fully enough at all time and context. To know the peoples' emotions, socio-cultural values and norms, their own organizations that deserve social capital and potentialities for their own developments considering these things would be significant.

An academic study (Kontinen, 2007) on small Finnish NGOs, done in Tanzania, states that NGOs have an important role in development co-operation through which development activities grew and it was seen as one way to strengthen civil society to provide potential for enhancing more effective development than the state, and to exercise participatory development.

A study done in Nepal (IPE, FBC & CPRA, 2010) shows that role of NGOs of marginalized and socially excluded communities/groups is important in achieving social inclusion particularly at policy level. For example, one-third of the total seats of the existing constituent assembly are represented by the indigenous nationalities (both male & female). Even NGOs of Dalits women, Indigenous Nationalities women, Madhesi women and other women NGOs also played significant role for achieving social inclusion of women in various sectors of the state (from bureaucracy to policy making level). But, they could not pay attention for ensuring social inclusion at lower level and local level as compared to the central or policy making level.

A theoretical discussion done by Lang (n.d.) focuses on NGOs' role in the participation, empowerment and social transformation of poor and marginalized groups, with particular reference to disabled people. The author attempts to prove NGOs' role in the disability sector's development in terms of mitigating inequalities through social inclusion, empowering through bottom-up/people-centric approach and transforming society by focusing to the oppressed. This theoretical discussion emphasizes the NGOs' roles that are played based on the foundation of

Paulo Freire's philosophy (1970) and Robert Chambers' approach (1983) to development of the marginalized groups. But it is not mentioned the NGOs' roles that have been seen in reality.

The World Bank (2002) emphasizes on empowerment of the peoples (every community). So many terms are used to define the 'empowerment'. To define the 'empowerment', in development context, basically four elements are used. These are: access to information; inclusion and participation; accountability, and local organizational capacity (World Bank, 2002, p. 14). As a development actor and agent, NGOs' roles are to facilitate and empower the community peoples. There are thousands of examples of empowerment strategies that have been initiated by poor people themselves and by governments, civil society, and the private sector (Viriyā, 2009, p. 16). Based on this discussion, in our context, we can say that NGOs of indigenous nationalities are both development actor and agent that represent and act for their own communities as well as other local communities.

Research Methods

This paper has been prepared using qualitative research approach and by collecting data from both primary as well as secondary sources. For primary data, I interviewed key board members and project staffs of the NGOs, and in small number of beneficiaries who were available in Kathmandu. In this process, open-ended and probing type questions were asked to get sufficient qualitative information. For secondary data, I reviewed/collected data from the relevant documents (both projects and organizations) of the concerned NGOs.

Introduction to the NGOs: INWOLAG and EMMF

There is not exact figure of the NGOs of indigenous nationalities. Many NGOs are working separately, and many NGOs work in coordination, and many NGOs are in networks and under an umbrella. NGO-Federation of Nepalese Indigenous Nationalities (NGO-FONIN) is

only one umbrella organization or federation of NGOs of Nepal's indigenous nationalities. According to the official record of the NGO-FONIN, it has 106 NGOs as members (upto December of 2011).

Although there are also ethnic organizations, which are generally known as socio-cultural organizations but legally they are also NGOs (if legally registered) and can act like other. The main differences between ethnic organizations and their NGOs are separated based on the membership and objectives. In an ethnic organization, membership is obtained by/given to only those persons who are from the same community and its objective would be development (it might include from culture to rights) of the same community. However, in their NGO, indigenous peoples from different ethnic communities can get/obtain its membership and its objectives would be development of not only a single community but also of all ethnic communities and it might be also for non-ethnic communities/groups like poor, Dalits etc. In this study, out of two, one NGO called Indigenous Women Legal Awareness Group (INWOLAG) falls in second category. Rarely, in some NGOs membership is limited to one ethnic community but it can work also for other communities including non-ethnic groups. In my study, another NGO namely Eighteen Magarat Magar Foundation [EMMF] (in Nepali -Athara Magarat Magar Pratisthan) lies in this category.

INWOLAG, established in 2000, is a Kathmandu based/national NGO of indigenous women lawyers. At present, there are 30 indigenous women advocates/license holder lawyers are its members including executive board members. It aims to promote legal rights of the indigenous women and raise awareness among the indigenous communities (INWOLAG, 2000). Its working area is all over the country.

Similarly, EMMF, established in 2059 BS, is a Kathmandu based/national NGO of Magars (for membership), who are originally dwellers in mid-west (particularly Rapti, Dhaulagiri and Bheri zone, which is called eighteen Magarat). Its branch is in Rolpa district. It aims to uplift the socio-economic status Magars and non-Magar marginalized groups/castes like all poor, and Dalits; and preserve and promote culture and language of Magars of that regions (EMMF, 2002a). Its working area is also Athar Magarat region.

Findings

In this section, I have described the major roles played by the two NGO of indigenous nationalities –namely INWOLAG and AMMF- their development.

Role of Indigenous Women Legal Awareness Group (INWOLAG)

Major roles of INWOLAG in the development of indigenous peoples have been categorized in the following ways:

Raising awareness. INWOLAG, in the funding support of donor agency and collaboration with other NGOs, carries out programs to make awareness the indigenous peoples about their rights and duties. For examples, in 2010, in the funding support of ILO regional office in Nepal, it accomplished sensitization program on ILO convention no. 169. Through this program, INWOLAG sensitized around 900 participants [who were representatives of the stakeholders and indigenous peoples' organizations (IPOs), and general public (most of them were indigenous nationalities) of 5 different districts] (INWOLAG, March 2011).

Similarly, INWOLAG has carried out several interaction programs and sensitization programs for community level indigenous nationalities in the contemporary issues, especially which are their concerns or concern of general public, in the coordination with district Bar Associations, ethnic organizations and NGOs of indigenous nationalities (both national and local)

(INWOLAG, 2010). For instance, it has conducted these kinds of programs in different topics like restructuring of state, federalism and rights of indigenous nationalities in new constitution, women rights, social inclusion, domestic and gender based violence and legal remedies etc.

(INWOLAG, 2009). From which, not only indigenous peoples in Kathmandu but also of district and community level got information on some contemporary hot issues and they became aware on their rights and concerns as well as way to seeking for solution. As a result, it was found that many cases of the indigenous women/victims have been come up to them. Mostly, cases are related to partition, property, kinship and domestic violence in inter-caste marriage (in personal communication with INWOLAG's secretary on 13th November 2011). They are providing support for their justice.

Supporting to get legal rights/justice. INWOLAG has been supporting to the indigenous women for getting their legal rights. As a legal advisor, its lawyers provide legal advice and aids/supports without cost for those who are really victims but cannot afford. Around, 40 women are getting this kind of supports. In this regards, cases of most of the victims are proceeded for justice and INWOLAG's member lawyers play role as advocates of the parties. Sometimes, they play mediator's role for arbitration of the parties (with justice to the victims). They are providing supports by advocating of a dozen of cases of victim women in the courts outside the Kathmandu valley. For this purpose, sometimes, they go to the corresponding districts themselves and, sometimes, they work by coordinating with local Bar association. It depends on needs but service cost is bear by the organization itself. Due to their support, more than a dozen indigenous women have got justice and around three dozen indigenous women have obtained reliefs and solved their problems (through arbitration process) (in personal communication with INWOLAG's secretary and treasurer on 13th November 2011).

Capacity building. INWOLAG has a roster of its member resource persons/trainers and it provides resource persons to deliver trainings and facilitate workshops on legal issues. Mostly, NGOs of indigenous peoples and ethnic organizations request the INWOLAG for resource persons and it provides accordingly (with or without charge, it depends on context). Through such type of service, INWOLAG has been contributing to the ethnic communities and their organizations in their capacity building or enhancing capacity of the staffs and board members of the organizations. According to the respondents, INWOLAG's this service and support has been contributing to improve in performance of the service taker organizations' staffs. Ultimately, it would be helpful in their community level development.

Role of Eighteen) Magarat Magar Foundation (EMMF)

Major roles of EMMF in the development of indigenous peoples have been categorized in the following ways:

Community mobilization and local resource utilization. EMMF's one of the working strategies is community mobilization and local resource utilization (EMMF, 2002b). When the foundation launches the development project at community level then they mobilize the community peoples and utilize the available resources as much as possible. For example, it has been implementing livelihood project under the funding support of PAF since 2004. Initially it was started in 5 VDCs of Rolpa district and, now as third phase, it is in 12 VDCs (EMMF, 2010). For this project, community peoples (who are women, indigenous/nationalities, Dalits and poor families) are involved as beneficiaries and they are running agriculture base (farming, aggro-forestry e.g. handloom, and animal husbandry) activities. Communities play active role for their development and EMMF plays role as facilitator and intermediary between the community and donors. Local resources (natural), products, local knowledge and skills have been used as an

improved form for the livelihood activities (in personal communication with a project staff of the EMMF on 11th November 2011).

Raising awareness. EMMF also conduct awareness raising programs on contemporary issues by using its own resources as well as in other funding supports. EMMF conducted awareness raising programs on hot national issues like social inclusion (in 2008) constituent assembly, federalism and restructuring of the state (in 2009); interaction on ILO-169 and indigenous peoples' rights (in 2010). These programs were carried out from central level (Kathamndu) to local level (district and communities) – Rolpa, Pyuthan and Dang (EMMF, 2008, 2009, 2010). These programs, to some extent, educated the indigenous peoples and made them aware on their existing status/position in the state and about their rights.

Start up of self-development. EMMF's role can be considered as the approach developed by Robert Chambers – putting the last first. Similarly, if we look at it in actor-oriented approach of development, we can find the EMMF as people-centred actor oriented. All of its members are representing from Magar communities and from the same regions where it has been working since its inception. Staffs are also from the same regions and communities. Even in the conflict period, it was established and it worked with the communities, for the communities and by the same communities. This is the need to feel good about oneself, and to belong and feel secure (Maiava, 2001, p. 219) from own efforts. Its president said, “We are exception. We were working in Rolpa even in the conflict time, when all NGOs came back from their real project areas and worked in district headquarter and its surrounding villages. The reason behind this was that we worked for the communities by heart because we were coming from the same communities and we have to go there and live together.” In such a way, we can consider that EMMF has been playing a role of ‘self-starter of self-development’.

Institutional development of the rural community. Through its projects, around 1,200 groups of the beneficiaries' families have been formed (each group includes 20 -30 families) (in conversation with project staff on 9th November 2011). There are not only Magars and other ethnic communities but also Dalits, poor families of Chhetri and Bahun caste. All are organized, they use groups as a platform where they share their common issues/problems, discuss and try to seek for solutions. It is participatory and, we can say, a starting of institutionalization of community development that promotes sustainability of the development.

Socio-economic uplift. NGOs' role that they have and can potentially play in the participation, empowerment and social transformation of poor and marginalized groups (Lang, n.d., p. 1). I found that EMMF's role is also matched with this view. It started own journey for the socio-economic uplift of the community peoples when it launched a 'women literacy class' in Dang in 2060 B.S. (EMMF, 2060 B.S.). Participant women were mostly indigenous and few of them Dalits, and all were migrated from Rukum, Rolpa, Salyan and Pyuthan. Later on skilled based income generation training was provided them and, then, supported them for income generation.

EMMF has been continuously implementing the livelihood program in the funding support of PAF since 2004 to till the study date. The foundation implements similar types of projects in the funding supports and collaboration with district level government offices like District Cottage Office, District Development Committee etc. NFDIN annually provides some amount of fund for social empowerment program (like awareness on contemporary issues and indigenous nationalities' rights related issues) and for small scale of livelihood projects. But it is found that most of the livelihood projects are concentrated in Rolpa district although it has vision to expand the projects in other districts. But because of budget limitation they could not

materialized their wish yet. Nevertheless, to some extent, EMMF is playing important role to uplift the socio-economic status of the community peoples who are really bypassed from the development stream of the government and I/NGOs (including local NGOs).

Preservation and promotion of language and culture. EMMF has been working for preservation and promotion of language and culture of Magar community of Athara Magarat regions. It has published a dictionary of 'Athara Magarat Magar language' in combined with Nepali and English language. It has prepared and published 'cultural documentaries' e.g. *Bhumya pooja* (worship of land by Magars), books and booklets. It has collected those traditional objects which represent the historical and socio-cultural heritage of Magars of that region. In its initiative, these sorts of objects have been put in the museum of indigenous nationalities that was in an office building of Nepal Tourism Board, Exhibition road of Kathmandu. I have went EMF's office and that museum many times, and also observed these heritages. Besides that, in similar museum situated in Kirtipur (and it is under construction), the foundation has set up the same historical and cultural heritages. EMMF also celebrates cultural feasts and festivals even in Kathmandu.

Capacity building/leadership development. EMMF conducts various capacity building trainings and workshop programs for enhancing capacity of the youths. Some of the programs were found related to career development for the fresh graduates. It is found that leadership development, presentation skill, effective communication skill, anchoring, news writing and report writing trainings became more useful for both youths and organization's peoples (members and project staffs). It helped them not only in their works but also in their daily life and they felt that level of their confidence increased (in personal communication with participants on 11th November 2011).

Discussion

In this section, I shall discuss the findings that are the roles of the two NGOs of indigenous nationalities in their community by linking with empowerment theory of development.

The terms 'empowerment' include self-strength, control, self-power, self-reliance, own choice, life of dignity in accordance with one's values, capable of fighting for one's rights, independence, own decision making, being free, awakening, and capability (Viriya, 2009, p. 15). It can be seen in various aspects of an individual like social, economic, political, professional etc. In the development context, four elements (which are: access to information; inclusion and participation; accountability, and local organizational capacity) of 'empowerment' stated by the World Bank (World Bank, 2002, p. 14) can be linked and that are discussed below.

One of the elements of the empowerment is 'access to information', which is considered as both resource and power. Informed citizens are better equipped to take advantage of opportunities, access services, exercise their rights, negotiate effectively, and hold state and non-state actors accountable (Viriya, 2009, p. 18). INWOLAG and EMMF have been playing role to empower the community peoples by informing them through their awareness and sensitization programs on various issues like social inclusion, rights of indigenous communities in ILO-169. Relevant, accessible and timely delivered information are always significant for getting further advantages by using or knowing it. For such, both NGOs have been working effectively and efficiently. For example, they conduct awareness programs on contemporary national issues and directly concerned with the targeted communities (like women rights).

One of the elements of the empowerment is 'inclusion and participation'. The World Bank (2002) explains 'inclusion and participation' focus on the 'who' and 'how' question

respectively. Or, who are included how and how they play role? Marginalized or socially excluded peoples like poor, Dalits, women, indigenous nationalities are included in the NGOs in different ways. For example, indigenous women lawyers can be member of INWOLAG and can play decision making role as per the organization rules and regulation. Indigenous nationalities women are the target groups/direct and prime beneficiaries of this NGOs. Various kinds of projects are launched for them – at central to community level. Besides, other NGOs or ethnic organizations get opportunities to participate in their activities and programs but it depending up on context and objectives of the programs. Similarly, in case of the EMMF, Magar can be its organization member but non-Magars particularly marginalized communities/groups like Dalit, poor, women get opportunities to be benefited from its projects. It has played remarkable role in formation of users groups under livelihood projects funded by the PAF. That provided opportunities to the community peoples to work themselves for their own development in meaningful as well as direct participation.

Another element of the empowerment mentioned by the World Bank is ‘accountability’.

Accountability refers to the ability to call public officials, private employers or service providers to account, requiring that they be answerable for their policies, actions and use of funds (Viriyā, 2009, p. 18). There are three main types of accountability mechanisms: political, administrative and public (ibid). Out of them, public or social accountability mechanisms that hold government agencies accountable to citizens are more concerned with community development and NGOs’ role to make aware both service providers/duty bearers and service takers/right holders. INWOLAG and EMMF have been playing role to make aware their community peoples about their rights and contemporary concerned issues (e.g. social inclusion) as well as sensitize the stakeholders about the public concerns and their responsibilities and

obligations. However, it could not have been measured the visible impacts in regards with accountability that might have ensured by the efforts of the community peoples. Citizen action or social accountability can reinforce political and administrative accountability mechanisms. It is continue process and it takes time to see what peoples we expect.

Another element is 'local organizational capacity', which refers to the ability of people to work together, organize themselves, and mobilize resources to solve problems of common interest (Viriya, 2009, p. 19). There is no necessary to be formal or structured organization. Around the world, including in war-torn societies, the capacity of communities to make rational decisions, manage funds, and solve problems was found in Indonesia (it is the case of in-depth study of 48 villages across Indonesia) (Chandrakirana, 1999). Organized communities are more likely to have their voices heard and their demands met than communities with little organization. Both INWOLAG and EMMF are also involved in the different networks e.g. NGO-FONIN, NGOs of indigenous nationalities. They also coordinate and work in collaboration with other ethnic organizations, professional organizations (e.g. Bar Association) and civil societies to advocate jointly for their identity, rights and interests. Besides, they also mobilize their own community peoples. Community peoples' membership-based organizations like users groups formed by EMMF's projects and both INWOLAG and EMMF themselves may be highly effective in meeting their own communities needs, but they are constrained by limited resources and technical knowledge. Regarding the mobilization of local resources, the target groups of the EMMF were found more capable than that of INWOLAG. The main reasons behind this it nature of the organizations and nature of their works or programmatic activities.

In this way, the indigenous nationalities (both men and women in EMMF's case and women in INWOLAG's case) are being empowered due to the roles played by their own two

NGOs. Empowerment, in other words, is enhancement of capabilities (in Sen's view) of these peoples.

Conclusion and Implication

NGOs' role to 'empower' individuals and communities has been an important part in the development sector. The role of the INWOLAG was found greater in its specific thematic issue (legal right of the indigenous nationalities women). Similarly, EMMF's role was found equally important in socio-economic development of the marginalized communities of mid-west Nepal. Based on this discussion, we can say that NGOs of indigenous nationalities are playing important role of development actor and agent in Nepal. In the view of empowerment theory, these NGOs are contributing to empower their own community. Role of these NGOs cannot be compared to all contexts because of their different nature, working sectors/thematic areas and organizational vision and goals. Specific working areas/themes and target groups, ownership feeling, commitment, self-motivation and devotion towards own communities are very important factors behinds seeing their role effective in the development of their own community.

Following areas of implications are pointed out:

- If we talk about the NGOs as development agent then role of these NGOs can be analyzed by linking with agency theories. Besides, if we look at it in beneficiaries' view then we can also discuss linking it with Sen's capability theory.
- An in-depth study is also important to explore that the outcomes and impacts due to the support/interventions of these NGOs.
- This discussion focused on empowerment but it would be better to study in-depth with measurement of empowerment by using indicators.

- Sometimes, NGOs roles are also mentioned as intermediary, planner, implementer, participant etc. We can discuss their role in this way.

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